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Time And Cost Management In Construction Projects In Owerri, Imo State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined time and cost management in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State. Two (2) research questions were posed for the study while descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study was 402,486 residents of Owerri and the sample for the study was 300 residents including; property developers, contractors and building materials dealers operating in Owerri which were selected using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a 10-item instrument styled “Time and Cost Management in Construction Projects Questionnaire (TCMCPQ)” structured by the researcher in the modified 4-points Likert scale model. The instrument was validated by the two experts in the Department of Estate Management. Reliability index of .80 was established with Cronbach alpha Coefficient. Mean and standard deviation statistics were used to answer the research questions. The results revealed that poor project planning and scheduling, delays in payment to contractors and suppliers, frequent design changes and variation orders, shortage of skilled labor and inadequate supervision and external factors such as bad weather, inflation, and government policy changes are major factors responsible for time overrun in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State among other findings. It was concluded that poor time and cost management result to delays in project completion, increased project expenses and abandonment of construction projects in Owerri, Imo State. From the findings, it was recommended among others that there should be proper project planning and scheduling with the aid of tools such as the Critical Path Method (CPM), Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT), or Gantt charts in order to identify task sequences, dependencies, and critical milestones and there should be effective communication among all stakeholders through open communication channels.

Keywords: Time Management in Construction Project, Cost Management in Construction Projects and Impact of Poor Time and Cost Management

INTRODUCTION

In developing economies like Nigeria, time and cost management remains a critical challenge facing the construction industry, which directly affects project profitability and sustainability with a ripple impact leading to a high incidence of project failures and disputes. The construction industry in Nigeria plays a vital role in national development by providing infrastructure, housing, and employment opportunities. However, the sector continues to face chronic challenges of time overruns and cost escalation, which undermine project performance and public confidence. In many cases, projects in Nigeria are not completed within the planned duration or budget, leading to abandonment, waste of resources, and failure to meet intended objectives. These challenges are often worsen by local factors such as fluctuating material costs due to economic instability, bureaucratic delays in approval processes, inadequate technical expertise, and socio-political issues.

Construction projects are acknowledged as complex endeavours that require the effective integration of scope, time and cost controls to achieve success. Their complex nature which encompasses numerous interconnected phases, diverse stakeholders, and unpredictable environmental variables

require robust management strategies to achieve meaningful success in construction project. Project time and cost performance are commonly used indicators of project success; delays and cost overruns undermine project objectives, erode client confidence, inflate budgets, and can stall development outcomes (Project Management Institute, 2017).

Time management in construction refers to the systematic process of planning, scheduling, monitoring, and controlling project activities to ensure completion within the specified timeframe (Kerzner, 2013). It involves defining project tasks, sequencing them logically, estimating activity durations, and developing a schedule that integrates resource availability and project milestones and typically using tools like the Critical Path Method (CPM) and Gantt charts. It is imperative to state that it is not only about setting deadlines but also about coordinating resources and activities efficiently to avoid delays and disruptions.

Cost management, on the other hand, involves all processes required to ensure that a project is completed within the approved budget. It encompasses cost estimation, budgeting, financing, expenditure tracking, and cost control throughout the project lifecycle. Hence, it is a continuous process that begins with preliminary cost forecasting during the planning stage and continues through to the post-construction evaluation stage often utilizing sophisticated techniques like Earned Value Management (EVM).

Owerri, as the state capital and a major construction hub in Imo State, has continued to experience persistent time and cost management challenges, which have reached an alarming level. Both public and private construction projects ranging from roads, schools, and hospitals to residential housing schemes frequently suffer from delays and budget overruns. Empirical evidence and project reports attribute these deviations to several factors, including poor planning and scheduling, fluctuations in material prices, inadequate project supervision, funding interruptions, and contractor inefficiencies (Okereke & Igwe, 2020). These recurrent challenges not only affect project delivery but also undermine economic development and public confidence in the construction sector within the region. These issues are further compounded by weak enforcement of contractual agreements, and lack of modern project management tools at the local level.

For state capitals like Owerri, Imo State, the rapid pace of urbanization and infrastructure development driven by government policies and private investment has intensified the demand for efficient project delivery. Therefore, this study is crucial as it seeks to move beyond general observations by empirically investigating the specific, critical factors that contribute to time and cost failure within construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.

Research Objectives

The aim of the study is to examine time and cost management in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Assess the major factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.
2. Assess the overall impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the major factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State?
2. What are the overall impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State?

Conceptual Review

Concept of Time Management in Construction Projects

Time management in construction projects refers to the systematic process of planning, organizing, and controlling project activities to ensure timely completion within specified constraints. Kiswati and Chasanah (2019) defined time management as the ability to prioritize, schedule, and execute tasks effectively to achieve project goals within the allocated time frame. According to Shehu (2021), it involves managing human behavior and operational activities in relation to time by adhering to planned schedules and established milestones to ensure project success. This means that time management in construction is a decision-making process that integrates optimization models to

balance time and cost, ensuring that project completion is achieved at minimal expense without compromising quality. For Akinola and Adeleke (2022) it is the strategic application of scheduling techniques, such as the Critical Path Method (CPM) and Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT), to monitor progress, identify potential delays, and maintain control over project timelines.

In construction management, time is one of the most critical performance indicators, alongside cost and quality. Olawale and Sun (2010) averred that effective time management enables contractors, clients, and project managers to coordinate resources efficiently, reduce idle time, and mitigate delays. It involves developing and implementing a detailed schedule that specifies project activities, durations, dependencies, and milestones. Hence, poor time management in construction often results from inadequate planning, delayed payments, design alterations, and supply chain disruptions. Therefore, effective time management is essential to enhance productivity, reduce rework, and ensure that projects are delivered according to the agreed timeline.

Empirical evidence supports the significance of time management as a determinant of project success. For instance, Oseghale, Abiola-Falemu, and Oseghale (2015) conducted a study in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria to identify factors affecting time and cost performance in construction projects. The study revealed that time overruns were primarily caused by delayed payments, material shortages, and lack of skilled labor. The authors concluded that effective planning and scheduling were essential in mitigating these delays.

Cost Management in Construction Projects

Cost management in construction projects refers to the systematic process of planning, estimating, allocating, and controlling financial resources to ensure that a project is completed within the approved budget. Lock (2013) defined cost management as all the procedures required to ensure that a project is delivered within its estimated financial plan while meeting the desired scope and quality standards. Memon, Rahman, and Azis (2012) define cost management as a coordinated process that includes cost estimation, cost budgeting, and cost control to maintain financial discipline throughout the project life cycle. It is the continuous process of forecasting, monitoring, and evaluating expenditures to ensure that project costs remain aligned with the planned objectives.

Cost management is a pertinent component of construction project success, as it ensures the efficient use of financial resources and prevents unanticipated expenses that could jeopardize completion. Memon et al. (2012) opined that the process begins with cost estimation, which involves predicting the total expenditure required for labor, materials, equipment, and overheads. Followed by cost budgeting, which allocates estimated costs to specific work packages or project components, providing a framework for financial monitoring and cost control which focuses on tracking actual expenditures against planned budgets and making adjustments when discrepancies occur. Effective cost management therefore helps contractors and clients maintain transparency, accountability, and financial predictability throughout the project life cycle.

Cost management is essential in construction because it directly influences project performance, financial viability, and client satisfaction. The importance of cost management is that it ensures projects are completed within budget, thereby minimizing financial risks to both contractors and clients. According to Kerzner (2013), effective cost management provides a financial baseline against which actual performance can be measured, enabling early detection of potential cost overruns.

Factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects

Time overruns which is also known as schedule delay occurs when a project exceeds its planned completion date, thereby affecting cost, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction. Different scholars have identified a wide range of factors responsible for such delays, which according to Olawale and Sun (2010) emanates from managerial inefficiencies, financial constraints, technical problems, and external environmental conditions.

Aibinu and Jagboro (2002) in their study identified poor project planning and scheduling as one of the major cause of time over run. They discovered that inadequate planning, unrealistic scheduling, and lack of proper coordination among project participants are the leading contributors to project delays in Nigeria. Their study revealed that over 70% of sampled projects in the Nigerian construction industry suffered delays due to poor supervision, late approvals, and inadequate contractor experience. Oseghale, Abiola-Falemu, and Oseghale (2015) identified financial difficulty and delayed payment as a factor that result to time over run. They discovered that delays in fund disbursement by clients,

coupled with inflation and cost fluctuations, significantly prolong construction timelines. The study, conducted in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, showed that 65% of projects experienced schedule slippage due to delayed payments, limited cash flow, and poor financial management. Similarly, Ameh and Osegbo (2011) in their study outlined design changes and variation orders as a significant cause of project delays. They opined that when clients or consultants alter the project scope or specifications after work has commenced, contractors are forced to revise plans, leading to disruptions and rework. According to Ameh and Osegbo (2011) frequent design modifications, change orders, and client indecision contributed heavily to project delays in Nigeria. Moreover, Kerzner (2013) stated that poor communication and stakeholder coordination contribute to time overruns. He averred that in complex construction environments involving multiple stakeholders—such as clients, contractors, consultants, and supplier’s ineffective communication can result in misunderstandings, conflict, and duplication of efforts. Another factor as identified by Okereke and Igwe (2020) that results to time over run is external factors such as adverse weather conditions, political instability, and regulatory delays also influence project timelines.

Impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects

Poor time and cost management practices remain a significant challenge in the construction industry, often leading to project delays, cost overruns, and poor performance. Akindele and Olukolajo (2020) opined that ineffective time and cost control mechanisms reduce productivity, cause budget inflation, and compromise project quality. Poor planning, inaccurate cost estimation, and inadequate monitoring systems frequently lead to delayed project delivery and resource wastage. One of the key impacts of poor time and cost management is schedule delay, which disrupts project sequencing and completion timelines. Arowoia and Ogunbayo (2019) opined that 68% of sampled construction projects in Southwestern Nigeria suffered time overruns caused by late payments, poor coordination, and insufficient supervision. This delay lead to increased overhead expenses in severe cases strain relationships between clients and contractors. Similarly, it can result to project abandonment, when delays and cost escalations become unsustainable, contractors may withdraw, or project owners may terminate funding. According to Ameh and Osegbo (2011) several Nigerian construction projects were abandoned due to prolonged time overruns and rising costs. Such abandonment results in wasted investments, loss of public trust, and environmental degradation caused by uncompleted structures. Another major consequence is cost overrun, where actual expenses exceed the approved budget. According to Dan-Asabe, Olanrewaju, and Mohammed (2021) weak financial control, material price fluctuations, and poor risk management were leading causes of cost escalation in public building projects in Northern Nigeria. These overruns reduce project profitability and limit the number of projects that can be completed within fiscal periods. Similarly, Ebekozien, Ogedengbe, and Aigbavboa (2022) averred that ineffective time and cost management practices lead to substandard project outcomes and loss of public confidence, particularly in government-funded infrastructure. When contractors rush to meet missed deadlines or reduce costs, they often compromise safety and material quality, resulting in future maintenance costs and early deterioration.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Resource-Based View (RBV), This theory posits that the successful management of project resources including labor, materials, and finances determines performance efficiency (Barney, 1991). According to Barney (1991), for a firm’s resources to provide a sustainable competitive advantage, they must possess four key attributes; they must be Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Non-substitutable (VRIN). Valuable resources enable a firm to exploit opportunities and neutralize threats in its environment. Rare resources are unique and not widely possessed by competitors. Inimitable resources are difficult for competitors to copy or replicate, while non-substitutable resources cannot be easily replaced by alternative assets or processes. According to Grant (1996), the theory emphasizes that internal competencies such as project planning skills, technical expertise, financial management systems, and organizational culture determine a firm’s ability to deliver projects efficiently.

The relevance of this theory to the study is that it emphasized on the importance of internal resource capabilities such; as skilled manpower, effective scheduling systems, financial discipline, and managerial competence as determinants of project success. Poor utilization of these resources often leads to time delays, cost overruns, and reduced quality, while effective resource management

enhances efficiency and project delivery outcomes. According to Ebekoziem, Ogedengbe and Aigbaybo (2022) firms that can manage their internal resources more effectively will be better positioned to complete projects within budget and schedule, giving them a competitive edge in the construction industry.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was descriptive survey and the population of the study was 402,486 residents of Owerri. The sample for the study was 300 residents including; property developers, contractors and building materials dealers operating in Owerri (Municipal, North and West), Imo State. The simple random sampling technique was employed to select the sample. The instrument of the study was a validated 10-item instrument styled “Time and Cost Management in Construction Projects Questionnaire (TCMCPQ)”, structured by the researcher in the modified 4-points Likert scale model and a reliability index of 0.87 was obtained using the Cronbach alpha method. Mean and standard deviation statistics were used to answer two research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Figure 1: Sex Distribution of Respondents

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The figure1 above shows the sex distribution of respondents with frequency. It shows that 270 respondents (90%) are male, while 30 respondents (10%) are female. The gender disparity observed in this study can be attributed to sociocultural, economic and contextual factors prevalent in Owerri and similar urban Nigerian settings.

Figure 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The figure 2 above shows the result of the distribution of respondents by age. The result indicates that 16.7% of the respondents were within the age bracket of 25-31 while 33.3% of the respondents were within the age bracket of 32-38 while 50% are within the age bracket of 39 and above.

Figure 3: Religious Distribution of Respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Figure 3 above shows the religious distribution of respondents. 270 respondents (90%) are Christians, 8 respondents (2.7%) are Muslim, and 20 respondents (6.7%) are traditionalist while those whose religious beliefs were not disclosed are 2 (0.7%).

Research Question 1: *What are the major factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State?*

Table 1: Mean of Respondents on the Major Factors Responsible for Time Overruns in Construction Projects in Owerri, Imo State

S/N	Items	Respondents (N=300)		
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	Remarks
1.	Poor project planning and scheduling contribute significantly to time overruns in construction projects	3.41	.67	Agreed
2.	Delays in payment to contractors and suppliers often cause interruptions and prolong project duration	3.43	.85	Agreed
3.	Frequent design changes and variation orders lead to construction delays and project time overruns.	3.10	.87	Agreed
4.	Shortage of skilled labor and inadequate supervision negatively affect project timelines	3.63	.57	Agreed
5.	External factors such as bad weather, inflation, and government policy changes cause time overruns in construction projects	3.23	.76	Agreed
Criterion mean =2.50				
Average		3.42	.74	Agreed

Legend

\bar{x}_1 =Mean

SD1= Standard Deviation

Scale

1.00—2.49= Disagree

2.50---4.00= Agree

Table 1 above revealed the major factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State. In item 1, respondents have a mean of 3.41, which means that respondents agreed that poor project planning and scheduling contribute significantly to time overruns in construction projects. In item 2, respondents have mean of 3.43 which revealed that respondents agreed that delays in payment to contractors and suppliers often cause interruptions and prolong project duration. In item 3, the mean of respondents is 3.10 which revealed that respondents agreed that frequent design changes and variation orders lead to construction delays and project time overruns. In item 4, the mean of respondents is 3.63 which show that respondents agreed that shortage of skilled labor and inadequate supervision negatively affect project timelines. In item 5, respondents have mean of 3.23 which reveals that respondents agreed that external factors such as bad weather, inflation, and government policy changes cause time overruns in construction projects.

In summary, with the aggregate mean of respondents (3.42) greater than the criterion mean of 2.50; respondents agreed on the major factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.

Research Question 2: *What are the overall impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State?*

Table 2: Mean of Respondents on the Overall Impact of Poor Time and Cost Management Practices in Construction Projects in Owerri, Imo State

S/N	Items	Respondents (N=300)		
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	Remarks
6.	Poor time and cost management practices cause frequent delays in project completion.	3.10	.70	Agreed
7.	Ineffective time and cost control leads to increased project expenses and cost overruns.	3.59	.59	Agreed

8.	Lack of proper time and cost management negatively affects the reputation and credibility of construction firms.	3.42	.67	Agreed
9.	Inefficient time and cost management contributes to project abandonment in the construction industry.	3.2	.70	Agreed
10.	Poor management of time and cost results in a decline in construction project quality.	3.48	.76	Agreed
Criterion mean =2.50 Average		3.36	.69	Agreed
Legend		Scale		
\bar{X}_1 =Mean		1.00—2.49= Disagree		
SD1= Standard Deviation		2.50---4.00= Agree		

Table 2 above revealed the overall impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State. In item 6, respondents have a mean of 3.10, which means that respondents agreed that poor time and cost management practices cause frequent delays in project completion. In item 7, respondents have mean of 3.59 which revealed that respondents agreed that ineffective time and cost control leads to increased project expenses and cost overruns. In item 8, the mean of respondents is 3.42 which revealed that respondents agreed that lack of proper time and cost management negatively affects the reputation and credibility of construction firms. In item 9, the mean of respondents is 3.20 which show that respondents agreed that inefficient time and cost management contributes to project abandonment in the construction industry. In item 10, respondents have mean of 3.48 which revealed that respondents agreed that poor management of time and cost results in a decline in construction project quality.

In summary, with the aggregate mean of respondents (3.36) greater than the criterion mean of 2.50; respondents agreed on the overall impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The major factors responsible for time overruns in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State

The first findings of the study (2025) is that poor project planning and scheduling, delays in payment to contractors and suppliers, frequent design changes and variation orders, shortage of skilled labor and inadequate supervision and external factors such as bad weather, inflation, and government policy changes are major factors responsible for time overrun in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.

This finding agrees with Aibinu and Jagboro (2002) who identified poor project planning and scheduling as one of the major cause of time over run. They discovered that inadequate planning, unrealistic scheduling, and lack of proper coordination among project participants are the leading contributors to project delays in Nigeria. Similarly, the finding agrees with Oseghale et al. (2015) who identified financial difficulty and delayed payment as a factor that results to time over run. Furthermore, the finding is in consonance with Ameh and Osegbo (2011) who in their study outlined design changes and variation orders as a significant cause of project delays.

A probable explanation to this trend to be that most person who responded to the questionnaire must have encountered or witnessed these challenges in the course of construction project in Owerri, Imo State.

Impact of poor time and cost management practices in construction projects in Owerri, Imo State

The second findings of the study (2025) is that poor time and cost management practices cause frequent delays in project completion, leads to increased project expenses and cost overruns,

negatively affects the reputation and credibility of construction firms, result to project abandonment and results in a decline in construction project quality.

The finding is in agreement with Akindele and Olukolajo (2020) who opined that ineffective time and cost control mechanisms reduce productivity, cause budget inflation, and compromise project quality. Hence, poor planning, inaccurate cost estimation, and inadequate monitoring systems frequently lead to delayed project delivery and resource wastage. Similarly, the finding is in tandem with Arowoiya and Ogunbayo (2019) opined that 68% of sampled construction projects in Southwestern Nigeria suffered time overruns. This delay lead to increased overhead expenses in severe cases strain relationships between clients and contractors. Furthermore, the finding agrees with Ebekozi et al, (2022) who averred that ineffective time and cost management practices lead to substandard project outcomes and loss of public confidence, particularly in government-funded infrastructure. The finding affirms the result of Ameh and Osegbo (2011) that several Nigerian construction projects were abandoned due to prolonged time overruns and rising costs.

A plausible explanation to this result could be that most persons who responded to the instrument may have had this experience in construction project.

CONCLUSION

Construction project are capital intensive and as such requires proper time and cost management for effective project completion and delivery. Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that poor time and cost management result to delays in project completion, increased project expenses and abandonment of construction projects in Owerri, Imo State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. In order to eliminate time overrun in construction projects, there should be proper project planning and scheduling with the aid of tools such as the Critical Path Method (CPM), Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT), or Gantt charts in order to identify task sequences, dependencies, and critical milestones.
2. There should be effective communication among all stakeholders through open communication channels in order reduce misunderstanding and resolve issues that can lead to project delays.
3. In order to reduce cost overrun cost control tools such as Earned Value Management (EVM) and Variance Analysis should be used by stakeholders in construction industry.

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